

The Effects of Flight Simulators in Pilot Training: A Systematic Review on Safety, Economic Impact and Professional Development

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>REVIEW ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Flight Training Pilot Training Flight Simulators Cost Career</p> <p>Received: 23 February 2026 Revised: 16 June 2026 Accepted: 22 June 2026</p>	<p>With the advancement of technology and the growing interest in aviation, pilot training has become increasingly complex and multidimensional. This study conducts a systematic literature review to examine the effects of flight simulators on pilot training and pilots' career development. The PRISMA 2020 model was applied, and academic publications published between 2000 and 2024 were reviewed using the Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus databases. Based on the identified keywords, an initial total of 372 studies were identified. After eliminating duplicate, irrelevant, and methodologically inadequate studies, 112 studies were included in the final analysis. The findings indicate that simulator usage is addressed within three main dimensions: training, cost, and career development. Within the training dimension, the contributions of simulators to flight safety were also evaluated. The results revealed that flight simulators provide significant benefits in pilot training, including the development of technical skills, the reduction of risks, and the optimization of training costs. However, disadvantages such as the high cost of simulators and their limited accessibility were also highlighted. The study emphasizes that future research should address technical, flight safety, and financial dimensions in an integrated manner and recommends the development of comprehensive collaborations and support mechanisms to enhance the effectiveness of simulator-supported training models.</p>

1. Introduction

Air transportation has become an increasingly preferred mode of transportation; however, it is also a field characterized by low tolerance for error and the need for high safety standards. In this context, pilot training is of vital importance for ensuring that pilots operating in commercial air transportation can maintain safety, efficiency, and professional competence. Analyses of past aviation accidents and studies on pilot training have revealed that the vast majority of incidents are attributable to human error. With technological advancements and the growing global interest in aviation, pilot training has become increasingly complex and multidimensional. Furthermore, considering the worldwide pilot shortage, it is evident that pilot training has

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become an extremely demanding and costly process in terms of both time and financial resources (Dekker, 2011; Possebon et al., 2023; Dornan et al., 2006; ScholarsArchive, Robert Graham and Robert, 2017; Broach, Schroeder and Gildea, 2019).

As noted above, pilot training imposes a significant financial burden on both pilot candidates and training institutions. According to Broach (2010), the annual cost of training at private flight training institutions outside universities is approximately USD 50,000, whereas the cost at university-affiliated flight schools may exceed USD 100,000. Today, due to increases in exchange rates and the growing complexity of aviation technologies, these costs have nearly doubled. Consequently, aviation authorities, airlines, and training institutions have turned toward seeking more economical, safer, and more sustainable training methods and tools. One of the most critical aspects of modern pilot training is ensuring that suitable candidates receive effective training within the shortest possible timeframe in response to advancing aviation technologies and increasing equipment costs (Şimşek et al., 2010). In this regard, flight simulators have become indispensable tools in contemporary pilot training due to their advantages in cost-effectiveness, safety, and measurable performance evaluation.

At this point, the original contribution of the present study becomes more apparent when compared with contemporary research in the field. For example, the systematic literature review conducted by Marques et al. (2023) on *Ab Initio Flight Training* focused on the technical dimensions of training processes and did not address the interconnected dimensions of training, cost, and career development from an integrated perspective. Similarly, Savaş et al. (2025) examined the overall contribution of flight simulators to training performance, whereas Somerville et al. (2025) focused specifically on the use of Extended Reality (XR) technologies.

A review of the existing literature indicates that studies on flight simulators have primarily focused on specific technological aspects of simulators or on individual dimensions such as operational effectiveness. Furthermore, studies that evaluate the effectiveness of flight simulators in pilot training, their financial implications, and their impact on pilots' professional lives from a holistic perspective remain relatively limited in the literature. Therefore, there is a need to assess the effects of flight simulators on pilot training through a comprehensive perspective in order to address this gap in the existing literature.

Against this background, the present study aims to examine the effects of flight simulators on pilot training and their role in pilots' career development from a multidimensional perspective, while also evaluating the cost dimension of simulator-based training. The study is based on a systematic literature review conducted in accordance with the PRISMA protocol, and the findings obtained were analyzed thematically based on evidence derived from the existing literature.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. The second section reviews the existing literature on flight simulators and pilot training within the framework of a systematic literature review. The third section presents the methodological framework of the study, providing a detailed explanation of the systematic literature review process, the databases used, the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the thematic analysis approach. The fourth section presents the findings obtained under the three main themes of cost, training, and career, and evaluates the trends identified in the literature. Finally, the fifth section summarizes the overall conclusions of the study, discusses the findings, and provides recommendations for future research.

2. Conceptual Framework

Following the Wright brothers' first powered flight in 1903, aviation developed rapidly and has evolved into a field integrated with advanced technology. Parallel to these developments, the need for pilot training emerged, and efforts began to provide pilots with a safe environment in which structured training could be delivered. These early initiatives laid the foundation for the first flight simulators. Over time, simulators have undergone continuous development and have become indispensable tools used at every stage of pilot training, particularly with the growing importance of aviation education (Allerton, 2009).

Considering the vital importance of safety, cost-effectiveness, and training quality in aviation, the methods used in pilot training must be regularly reassessed and updated. The growing global demand for pilots and the increasing costs of flight training have led to a rise in research focusing on the role of simulators in training.

However, a large portion of the existing literature concentrates on only a single aspect of simulator technology, while its broader impacts on cost, training effectiveness, and pilots' career development have not been sufficiently examined from a holistic perspective.

This study provides an original contribution to the literature by systematically analyzing the role of flight simulators in pilot training and pilots' career development, while also incorporating the cost dimension into the evaluation.

2.1. The Evolution of Simulators in Pilot Training

During the early stages of aviation education, training was generally conducted on the ground using simple mechanical devices and verbal instructions. The Sanders Teacher, developed in 1910, is considered one of the first attempts to create a structured flight training device. This apparatus consisted of a simple cockpit that could be adjusted according to wind direction, and its effectiveness was largely dependent on weather conditions. As wind intensity increased, the training experience became more realistic for the pilot (Allerton, 2009; Ray L, 2000). Despite its limitations, the Sanders Teacher remained in active use for pilot training until the end of World War I (Boztaş, 2012).

These early applications demonstrated the potential of simulators in pilot training; however, the inherent limitations of mechanical systems created the need for more advanced designs. In this context, the Link Trainer, developed by Edwin Link in the early 1930s, is widely recognized as the precursor of modern flight simulators (Ivan and Jana, 2012).

With the increasing importance of instrument flight training—also known as “blind flying”—the Link Trainer became widely used in basic flight training and was gradually adopted by both civilian flight schools and military institutions (Ray L, 2000). Figure 1. illustrates the cockpit layout of the Link Trainer.

Fig. 1. Link Trainer Flight Simulator (NASFL Museum, Access Date: September 2025)

With the outbreak of World War II, the demand for pilots increased at an unprecedented rate, and the need to train large numbers of pilots rapidly and safely accelerated the development of simulation technologies (Ray L, 2000). Following the end of the war, the knowledge and experience gained in military environments began to be transferred to civil aviation, paving the way for the widespread use of simulators in civilian pilot training. The integration of analog computers marked a significant milestone, making it possible to model more complex flight dynamics and operational processes in a more realistic manner (Ray L, 2000).

Between 1965 and 1980, analog systems were gradually replaced by digital technologies, and this transformation advanced further after 1985 with the incorporation of microelectronic components into

simulator architectures. These technological developments enabled simulators to operate with higher-capacity and faster processors (Ivan and Jana, 2012).

By the 1990s, hydraulic motion platforms had been replaced by microprocessor-controlled actuators capable of reaching frequencies above 500 Hz. This advancement significantly improved motion accuracy and control precision, thereby providing a higher level of realism in simulator-based training in terms of both motion and response characteristics (Allerton, 2009).

Today, this process of technological development continues unabated. Improvements in visual system resolution, increasingly precise modeling of flight dynamics, and the ability to synchronize motion systems with a high degree of accuracy have enabled flight simulators to provide an experience that closely resembles real flight environments. Consequently, the critical role of simulator technologies in pilot training continues to grow in importance (Wang et al., 2018).

2.2. The Role of Flight Simulators in Pilot Training

Numerous accidents throughout the history of aviation have prompted aviation authorities such as EASA (European Union Aviation Safety Agency) and the FAA (Federal Aviation Administration) to continuously review and revise pilot training standards. For example, following the crash of Colgan Air Flight 3407 in 2009, the FAA significantly tightened the requirements related to pilot training. Within this framework, the minimum flight time required for candidates seeking to obtain an Airline Transport Pilot Licence (ATPL) was increased from 250 hours to 1,500 hours.

The extension of training durations and the resulting increase in costs place considerable pressure on pilot candidates, causing some students to withdraw from training programs before completion (ScholarsArchive, Robert Graham and Robert, 2017; Somerville, Lynar and Wild, 2023). Changes in pilot licensing standards and the prolonged time required to complete training not only increase training expenses but also contribute to the growing global pilot shortage (Gorowsky, 2019; Marvin, 2016).

According to Boeing projections cited by Gorowsky (2019), approximately 117,000 commercial pilots will be needed in North America alone during the 20-year period following 2019. In light of these trends, numerous studies have highlighted the critical role of flight simulators in pilot training. These studies emphasize that simulators are widely used not only during specific stages of flight training but also in areas such as skill development, emergency procedure training, and Crew Resource Management (CRM) (Bürki-Cohen et al., 2009; Dinçer, 2023; Kozuba and Bondaruk, 2014).

Referring to the effectiveness of the highest simulator category, the Full Flight Simulator (FFS), Aydoğan (2023) stated that when pilot training institutions utilize FFS devices, dependence on real flight environments during the training process is significantly reduced. In this respect, the findings of Aydoğan (2023) support the conclusions reported in the studies discussed above.

2.3. Cost-Effectiveness of Simulators

Aviation training methods and tools are inherently based on advanced technologies due to the nature of the industry. The necessity of maintaining the highest levels of flight safety results in training equipment that is both technologically sophisticated and highly expensive. This cost structure affects not only training institutions but also pilot candidates directly. The financial burden of training may prevent some candidates from completing their education or limit their access to the piloting profession. Considering the global pilot shortage, the high cost of pilot training is regarded as one of the significant structural factors contributing to this issue. Furthermore, the studies reviewed in this research reveal that many institutions are unable to conduct actual flight operations due to high expenses associated with aircraft acquisition and fuel costs (Duggar, Smith and Harrison, 2009; Possebon et al., 2023; Adanov, Macintyre and Efthymiou, 2020; Biertümpfel, Annon and Pfifer, 2024).

Orlady (2010) emphasized the substantial financial burden associated with flight training, stating that many pilots begin their professional careers with approximately USD 100,000 in debt. Similarly, Balcerzak and Kostur (2018) examined how airlines are affected by the financial demands of training processes and reported that the

annual training cost for an airline employing 1,000 pilots reaches approximately USD 60 million. This finding demonstrates that training expenses impose considerable financial pressure on aviation organizations not only at the individual level but also at the institutional level (Balcerzak & Kostur, 2018).

The vast majority of studies reviewed in this research emphasize that flight simulators provide significant advantages not only in terms of training effectiveness but also from a cost perspective. Simulators allow complex systems introduced by technological innovations to be practiced in a risk-free environment while simultaneously contributing to the reduction of various cost elements (Dahlström, 2007). In addition to these benefits, simulators offer advantages in terms of maintenance and repair. Compared with actual aircraft, their lower maintenance requirements enhance operational continuity and help keep training costs under control (Biertümpfel, Annon and Pfifer, 2024).

Balcerzak and Kostur (2018) highlighted the advantages of simulator technology and drew particular attention to the long-term cost-effectiveness of simulator investments. In their study, they reported that flight simulators are used for more than 20 hours per day on average, and that this high utilization rate enables such investments to amortize themselves within approximately 15 years.

2.4. The Role of Simulators in Pilots' Career Development Process

The aviation industry, by its nature, is a field that closely follows and is directly influenced by technological developments. In this context, the piloting profession stands out as an occupation that requires the continuous renewal and updating of knowledge and skills. Therefore, the role of flight simulators in pilots' career development is of critical importance, as simulators enable pilots to meet these requirements both during their initial training and throughout various stages of their professional careers.

With advances in technology, modern aircraft and their onboard systems have become increasingly composed of sophisticated digital and electronic components (Dekker, 2011; Dornan et al., 2006; Thomas, 2016). As a result, both cockpit structures and pilot responsibilities have undergone significant changes. For example, whereas cockpit crews in the 1950s typically consisted of five members, this number has been reduced to two—a captain and a first officer—in modern commercial aviation as a consequence of the developments described above (Dinçer, 2023). Accordingly, the flight simulators used in pilot training today have diversified in order to accommodate evolving cockpit roles and operational requirements. In this regard, simulator classifications have been standardized by major aviation authorities such as the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), EASA, and the FAA.

Due to the constantly evolving and dynamic nature of the aviation industry, both the piloting profession and pilot training have become increasingly complex. In this context, the competencies expected from pilots are no longer limited to technical knowledge alone but also require all personnel involved in flight operations to cooperate effectively and in a coordinated manner. Furthermore, high training costs, lengthy training periods, and the limitations faced by training institutions in accessing expensive aviation equipment make the pilot training process even more challenging. The critical importance of flight simulators in pilot training and their role in mitigating these challenges have been widely discussed in the literature.

Nowakowski and Makarewicz (2018) drew attention to the Part-FCL regulations issued by EASA. According to these regulations, up to approximately 70% of the total training time in Instrument Rating (IR) programs may be completed in a simulator environment. The study also emphasized that this practice has significant potential to reduce training costs and improve the efficiency of training resource utilization.

Similarly, Kozuba and Bondaruk (2014) reported that students undergoing Instrument Flight Rules (IFR) training can complete approximately 40 of the required 55 training hours using FNPT II class simulators. The study further indicated that pilot candidates enrolled in Commercial Pilot Licence (CPL) training programs are able to complete approximately 20% of their total training in a simulator environment. Studies in the literature demonstrate that flight simulators are not only beneficial during the initial stages of pilot training but also serve as indispensable tools for maintaining professional competence, fulfilling licence renewal requirements, and assessing pilot performance throughout their careers. In this respect, simulator technologies are regarded as a

strategic component that provides cost-effectiveness in pilot training while supporting the sustainability of aviation safety.

In contrast, the present study addresses this gap in the literature by analyzing the multidimensional effects of flight simulators on training, cost, and career development themes, thereby providing a complementary contribution to existing systematic reviews.

3. Methodology

In this study, a systematic literature review method was employed to examine the effects of flight simulators on pilot training and pilots' career development. The methodological framework was structured in accordance with the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) model.

In this context, the PRISMA protocol stands out as a reporting standard based on the principles of transparency, accuracy, and reproducibility in systematic review studies. The PRISMA guidelines provide a structured methodological framework for every stage of the review process, from defining the research question and selecting data sources to establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria and reporting the results. This framework ensures that the literature review is conducted not only comprehensively but also with a high degree of scientific rigor. Furthermore, it facilitates the systematic identification of gaps in the literature and supports the reliable synthesis of existing evidence. In this respect, PRISMA is particularly important for maintaining methodological integrity in review studies conducted within interdisciplinary and dynamic fields such as aviation.

Today, flight simulators have become an indispensable component used at nearly every stage of pilot training. However, the multi-layered nature of pilot training, the high cost of the technological equipment used in training, and the increasingly stringent minimum flight-hour requirements imposed by aviation authorities such as EASA and the FAA have made the training process more challenging in terms of both time and cost. These conditions significantly increase the need for resource planning and management not only for individual pilot candidates but also for training institutions. Furthermore, rising training costs and extended training durations contribute to the growing global pilot shortage. Therefore, the systematic examination of simulator-based training is of critical importance for providing a comprehensive overview of existing scientific knowledge and identifying gaps in the literature.

In this context, the systematic literature review conducted in this study was structured in accordance with the defined review process. The methodological steps applied during the review—including the formulation of the research question, the selection of databases and keywords, the development of inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the systematic analysis of the studies—are explained step by step below. Prior to initiating the search process, a specific time frame was selected to ensure that the study was conducted in a systematic and focused manner. Accordingly, only studies published between January 2000 and December 2024 were included in the analysis.

A systematic literature review is a structured research approach based on a rigorous, traceable, and reproducible methodology aimed at synthesizing existing scientific studies within the framework of a specific research question or problem area (Çınar, 2021; Yıldız, 2021).

In this study, the systematic review process was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA framework. In order to ensure transparency and to perform a comprehensive and organized analysis, all methodological steps of the review were structured in line with the process outlined below. This process is visualized in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. PRISMA flow diagram used in the study

3.1. Determination of the Research Question

The first and most critical step of a systematic literature review is the clear and purpose-oriented formulation of the research question. This stage not only defines the scope of the study but also determines which studies will be included in the review, the criteria by which they will be evaluated, and how the analytical process will be structured. A clearly defined research question reduces potential conceptual ambiguities in subsequent stages and contributes to conducting the review in a more systematic and traceable manner (Çınar, 2021).

In this context, the primary research question guiding the present study was defined as follows: “To what extent are flight simulators effective tools in pilot training and pilots’ career development processes?”

Based on this research question, the role of simulators in training processes, their contributions to the aviation industry, and their cost-related aspects were examined from a multidimensional perspective. The research question was structured not only to encompass the technical and pedagogical aspects of simulator use but also to include their cost-effectiveness and contributions to professional development.

3.2. Selection of Databases and Identification of Keywords

The rapid growth of digital information resources in recent years has led to the emergence of numerous academic databases that provide access to high-quality publications across different disciplines. Since each of these databases offers content focused on specific subject areas, selecting the most appropriate databases is

of great importance for conducting a systematic literature review in a comprehensive, reliable, and purpose-oriented manner.

In addition, keyword search terms must be carefully identified to ensure that the search process focuses only on relevant studies and avoids unnecessary duplication. For this purpose, keyword sets are combined using Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT); this approach helps narrow the scope of the search while enhancing its systematic structure and traceability (Çınar, 2021).

In this study, Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus were selected to ensure broad and up-to-date access to the literature within the scope of the systematic review. The search strategy employed the primary keywords “flight simulator training,” “pilot training,” and “flight training,” while additional terms such as “airplane,” “commercial,” and “cost” were included to broaden the scope of the search. All selected terms were combined in various ways using Boolean operators in order to optimize the search process and ensure the systematic identification of publications included in the review. The search indices used in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Search Indices Used in the Study

Search Option	Search Index
Title – Keyword – Search Index	Pilot Training OR Flight Training OR Flight Simulator Training AND Commercial AND Airplane AND Cost

During the review process, the search was not limited solely to publications in English. Additional searches were also conducted within the same databases (Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus) using Turkish keywords such as “uçuş simülatorü eğitimi” (flight simulator training), “pilot eğitimi” (pilot training), and “uçuş eğitimi” (flight training). However, due to the limited number of publications available in Turkish, the main analysis was conducted based on international English-language publications. Accordingly, the systematic literature review was carried out in accordance with PRISMA guidelines, and studies published between January 2000 and December 2024 were comprehensively examined in the Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus databases using the predefined keywords.

3.3. Establishment of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

In a systematic literature review, it is necessary to define in advance which studies will be included in the analysis and which will be excluded. Clearly establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria enhances the transparency and reliability of the review process (Yıldız, 2021). In this context, factors such as publication type, language, publication year, and relevance to the research topic play a decisive role.

In line with the systematic review approach adopted in this study, the primary objective was to access literature directly related to pilot training and the use of flight simulators. For this purpose, the keywords “flight simulator training,” “pilot training,” and “flight training” were selected as the main search terms. Additional terms such as “airplane,” “commercial,” and “cost” were also incorporated into the search strategy to support the scope of the topic.

Conversely, studies that were not directly related to pilot training or that involved concepts from different disciplines—such as “virtual reality,” “UAV,” “drone,” and “helicopter”—were excluded from the review. This approach ensured that the search remained focused exclusively on the training of pilots operating manned civil aircraft and on literature addressing the dimensions of cost, training effectiveness, and career development. The inclusion and exclusion criteria, together with their justifications, are presented in detail in Table 2.

Table 2. Annotated Table of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Criterion Type	Criterion	Rationale / Explanation
Inclusion	“Flight Simulator Training”, Pilot Training”, “Flight Training”	These are the fundamental concepts that directly focus on the pilot training process.
Supporting Terms	“Airplane”, Commercial”, Cost”	These are supporting keywords related to commercial aircraft, civil pilot training, and the cost dimension..
Exclusion	“Virtual Reality”, “UAV”, “Drone”, “Helicopter”	These represent concepts that fall outside the scope of the study or belong to different disciplines; in particular, they cover topics that are not related to manned aircraft.

Furthermore, the explicit incorporation of these criteria into the PRISMA flow diagram strengthened the systematic nature and traceability of the review process.

3.4. Screening and Preliminary Evaluation of Sources

The studies identified through the literature search conducted using the predefined keywords were classified under three main thematic areas: training, cost, and career. This thematic structure enabled a comprehensive evaluation of the effects of flight simulators on pilot training and professional development processes.

The themes were determined based on the research focus of the studies included in the analysis. It was observed that the majority of the reviewed publications concentrated on the effectiveness of training processes, the cost dimension of simulator use, and pilots’ professional development. Therefore, the thematic classification was structured around the three main themes of training, cost, and career. Flight safety was considered an integral component of the training theme and was not treated as a separate theme.

During the thematic analysis process, studies were not classified under a single theme only. When the content of a publication was related to more than one theme, the study was coded under all relevant themes. Consequently, the total frequency of themes may exceed the total number of 112 studies included in the review.

Approximately 12,010 results were obtained from the Google Scholar database; however, due to the platform’s technical limitations, only the first 100 pages of results could be accessed. As a result, a total of 3,000 records were manually reviewed, and 344 studies were included in the preliminary evaluation stage. The Web of Science search identified 113 publications; of these, 21 studies were considered suitable for evaluation, while 92 publications were excluded because they were either irrelevant to the topic or duplicates. In the Scopus database, 310 results were obtained; however, only 7 studies met the inclusion criteria, while 303 records were excluded for various reasons.

Due to the technical structure of Google Scholar, search results cannot be viewed beyond approximately the first 100 pages. Therefore, the review was limited to the first 3,000 accessible records. This limitation was acknowledged as a constraint of the study, and it should be recognized that some relevant studies appearing beyond these results may not have been included in the review.

Across the three databases, a total of 372 studies were identified as potential candidates for evaluation; however, nine publications could not be accessed. All identified studies were examined in detail at the title, abstract, and full-text levels. Duplicate records were removed, and publications that were not directly related to the research topic, were methodologically inadequate, or failed to meet the quality criteria were excluded from the review. Following this multi-stage screening process, the final study pool was reduced to 112 academic sources.

In addition to the publications included within the PRISMA framework, various guidelines, regulations, and technical reports were reviewed to establish the conceptual background of the study; however, these documents were not included in the systematic review. The research was based exclusively on published

academic studies, and no field data, surveys, or interviews were utilized. Furthermore, military aviation was excluded due to its specialized nature, and the review was limited to civil and commercial aviation training. Similarly, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) and virtual reality (VR) applications were excluded from the analysis, and the review was restricted to studies published in Turkish and English. These methodological limitations and exclusion procedures were considered essential elements in strengthening the methodological rigor and scientific integrity of the review.

3.5. Visualization of the Process Using the PRISMA Diagram

All stages of the literature review process are presented in Figure 3 using a flow diagram prepared in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines. The diagram systematically illustrates the number of studies included in the review as well as the reasons for excluding records from the analysis.

Fig. 3. PRISMA Flow Diagram for the Systematic Literature Review

3.6. Data Extraction and Analysis

A systematic data extraction process was applied to the 112 sources identified at the end of the four-stage methodological procedure. Within this scope, each publication was examined in detail with regard to author information, year of publication, country of publication, and thematic relevance to the study (training, cost, or career).

Through this structured data extraction process, the publications were organized in a manner that enabled their systematic classification and analysis within the framework of thematic analysis.

3.7. Thematic Coding and Synthesis

After completing the stages described above, common themes across the studies were identified, and a content analysis was conducted based on the data obtained. This analytical process facilitated a multidimensional understanding of the research topic while enabling the systematic synthesis of the findings.

Thematic analysis strengthens the scientific contribution of the review by facilitating the identification of relationships among similar studies, revealing common trends, and identifying gaps in the existing literature.

4. Findings

In this section, the findings obtained from the sources identified through the systematic literature review are analyzed under three main themes: cost, effectiveness in the training process, and impact on pilots' career development. In addition, the fractional contribution method was employed to more accurately reflect the distribution of multi-author and multinational publications. This approach enabled a more balanced assessment of each country's contribution to the literature. Figure 4. presents the fractional contribution distribution graph illustrating the proportional contributions of countries to the existing literature.

Fig. 4. Pareto Analysis of Countries' Fractional Contributions to the Literature

An examination of countries' contributions to the literature reveals clear differences in regional concentrations and levels of scientific productivity. The findings indicate that the United States has the highest contribution rate in this field. This situation can be attributed not only to the country's extensive airspace but also to its advanced aviation infrastructure and well-established institutional framework for flight training.

Research on aviation education and simulation technologies in the United States is not limited to academic institutions alone; it is also supported through collaborations among private flight schools, universities, and industry organizations. This multi-stakeholder structure enhances research diversity and facilitates the implementation of technological innovations in aviation training (Kozuba and Bondaruk, 2014; Zhu and Chen, 2024).

In addition, national regulatory authorities such as the FAA serve as reference institutions that establish aviation standards not only within the United States but also on a global scale (Rice, 2019; Wang et al., 2018). Training models and safety protocols developed by the FAA are either directly adopted by many countries or integrated into national regulations after being adapted to local conditions. Furthermore, the fact that certain components of training programs offered by aviation institutions in various countries are conducted in the United States reinforces the country's position as an international center for pilot training. This situation increases both student mobility and academic-industry collaboration, thereby strengthening the influence of the United States within the global aviation knowledge production network.

As a result, the United States has become a global hub for aviation training. Consequently, a substantial proportion of both theoretical and applied studies on flight simulators, training standards, and pedagogical approaches originate from the United States (Cookson, 2008; Zhu and Chen, 2024).

In terms of publication volume, Türkiye ranks second after the United States. In recent years, a noticeable increase has been observed in academic productivity both in the broader field of aviation and specifically in pilot training. Master's and doctoral theses conducted within university aviation faculties, nationally funded academic projects, and conference papers are among the primary factors strengthening Türkiye's regional contribution (Aydoğan, 2023; Boztaş, 2012; Şimşek et al., 2010).

Countries making moderate contributions to the literature include Poland, Australia, Slovakia, the Netherlands, and Germany. Research conducted in these countries primarily focuses on case studies, innovative training approaches, and simulation-based application methods, thereby contributing both quantitative and qualitative diversity to the literature. Overall, the distribution of studies in the literature indicates that simulation-based research is predominantly conducted by countries with well-developed aviation industries. Nevertheless, interest in aviation training and simulation technologies has been increasing steadily in countries located in different geographical regions in recent years.

This trend has progressed in parallel with growing investments in the aviation sector, particularly in developing countries, making simulator-based training research an increasingly widespread field of study on a global scale. The analyses also indicate a clear upward trend in the number of publications over time. While the number of studies directly addressing the topic between 2000 and 2010 was relatively limited, interest increased rapidly after 2011. In particular, during the period from 2016 to 2023, several publications were added to the literature each year, while 2024 was identified as the year with the highest number of publications.

These findings demonstrate that interest in the role of flight simulators in pilot training and professional development has strengthened considerably in recent years, in parallel with technological advancements. Therefore, the growth observed in the literature reflects not only a quantitative increase but also a trend toward greater interdisciplinary depth. Figure 5. presents the distribution of the publications examined in this study by year, together with the overall trend graph.

Fig. 5. Distribution of Publications by Year (Trend Graph)

An examination of Figure 4.2 reveals a noticeable increase in the number of publications after 2010. The period between 2000 and 2010 represents an initial stage during which studies directly focusing on the topic were relatively limited. In contrast, from 2011 onward, scientific interest in flight simulators and pilot training increased steadily.

The continuous upward trend observed between 2016 and 2023 indicates a growing concentration of both theoretical and applied studies in this field. The year 2024 was identified as the period with the highest number of publications, clearly demonstrating the increasing relevance and academic importance of the research topic. The overall trend suggests that, in recent years, flight simulators have not only been examined within the context of educational technologies but have also been investigated from multidimensional perspectives, including

cost, safety, and career development. This pattern indicates that the studies have focused on diverse themes such as cost, training, and career development.

To provide a clearer understanding of the overall trend and the qualitative structure of the literature, the publications included in the analysis were classified according to publication type. The findings indicate that the literature is predominantly composed of peer-reviewed journal articles (61 studies). These are followed by conference proceedings (29), theses (10), reports (8), and book chapters (4), respectively.

This distribution demonstrates that academic interest in the field is sustained not only through theoretical approaches but also through applied and interdisciplinary perspectives. A visual representation of the data obtained in this study is presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the 112 Publications by Type

In addition, the total of 112 studies identified in the literature were classified according to publication type (e.g., journal articles, conference proceedings, theses, reports, and similar sources). The overall distribution of the three main themes is visually presented in Figure 7.

An examination of the thematic distribution of the 112 publications analyzed within the scope of this study indicates that 55 focus directly on the cost theme, 105 on the training theme, and 35 on the career theme. Studies categorized under the cost theme emphasize concrete economic aspects such as the financial dimension of pilot training, the initial investment costs of simulators, and cost comparisons between real flight training and simulator-based training.

Studies classified under the training theme primarily focus on topics such as the comparison of different pilot training methods, the effects of simulator use on learning outcomes, and the evaluation of training effectiveness.

Research grouped under the career theme addresses the contributions of simulator-based training to pilots' professional development processes, competency acquisition, and career progression.

Fig. 7. Distribution of the 112 Publications by Type

4.1. Cost-Effectiveness of Simulator-Based Training

Recent technological developments in aviation have led to a qualitative transformation in the structure of flight operations. As a result of this transformation, flight operations have become increasingly team-oriented, and the piloting profession has consequently evolved into a more complex and multidisciplinary field (Dahlström, 2007).

In this context, the concept of cost encompasses various components, including simulator investment expenditures, operational costs, and training-related expenses. The high-cost nature of aviation training can negatively affect students pursuing careers in this field and may limit participation in training programs. Consequently, the literature increasingly emphasizes approaches aimed at reducing these costs and eliminating factors that negatively influence student motivation (Adanov et al., 2020; Boztaş, 2012; Broach et al., 2019; Corman, 2023; Dubena and Thomas, 2024; Galant et al., 2019; Şimşek et al., 2010).

Due to the high cost of flight training and airspace limitations in many countries, some nations, such as China, conduct pilot training in the United States, which offers more extensive airspace and a more advanced training infrastructure (Zhu and Chen, 2024). This situation clearly demonstrates the determining influence of airspace availability and infrastructural capacity on training costs, while also highlighting economic factors as one of the primary drivers of international training mobility.

Avendaño and Wilkins (2024) examined the total cost of a four-year pilot training program at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University and reported that the process imposes a financial burden exceeding USD 260,000. This finding further reinforces concerns regarding the economic accessibility of pilot training.

A similar cost structure is also evident in Türkiye. According to official statements issued by the Directorate General of Civil Aviation (DGCA), the training fee required for pilot candidates seeking to obtain an ATPL licence in Türkiye is approximately €80,000 (Directorate General of Civil Aviation, 2025).

Furthermore, Table 3, prepared on the basis of the 2025 ÖSYM Higher Education Programs and Quotas Guide, presents a comparative overview of the tuition fees charged by universities offering pilot training programs in Türkiye (Higher Education Programs and Quotas Guide, 2025).

Research on the cost structure of simulators indicates significant investment differences among simulator categories. Reweti et al. (2017) reported that entry-level PCATD simulators cost approximately NZ\$20,000 on average, whereas more advanced FTD simulators may reach investment levels of up to NZ\$500,000.

Nevertheless, despite their high initial acquisition costs, numerous studies have demonstrated that simulators provide substantial long-term cost advantages compared with real flight training.

Table 3. Semester-based tuition fees of pilot training programs at universities listed in the ÖSYM guide (YKS, 2025)

University Name	*Tuition Fee (\$)
Özyeğin University	32.000
Istanbul Okan University	21.500
Atılım University	20.000
Girne University	20.000
Antalya Bilim University	18.000
KTO Karatay University	17.000
Istanbul Nişantaşı University	16.000
Istanbul Aydın University	14.000
Girne American University	11.000

Indeed, Lazic et al. (2022) reported that one hour of actual flight training costs approximately €400 on average, whereas simulator-based training for the same duration ranges between €50 and €100. When these figures are considered together, it becomes evident that the use of simulators—particularly during the initial stages of pilot training—provides substantial cost savings for training institutions.

In addition to the advantages offered by simulators in terms of investment costs and hourly training expenses, the structural redesign of training programs also holds significant potential for reducing overall costs. In this regard, Possebon et al. (2023) found that the systematic integration of scenario-based training practices into pilot training programs could reduce the overall financial burden on both students and training institutions by approximately 20–25%.

This finding demonstrates that not only the use of simulators themselves but also the design of simulator-based training programs plays a critical role in improving cost-effectiveness.

4.2. Effectiveness of Flight Simulators in the Training Process

The training theme was addressed in the vast majority of studies included in the systematic literature review, indicating that the role of flight simulators in pilot training has been extensively examined in the literature. A significant number of studies emphasize that, despite technological advancements, the desired reduction in accidents caused by human error has not been achieved. This finding suggests that certain aspects of current training practices remain insufficient (Longridge et al., 2001). Figure 8. illustrates the proportion of human factors in aviation accidents between 1903 and 2018.

Aleksandrovich (2024) states that the primary objective of pilot training is to ensure the sustainability of safe flight operations. According to the author, training consists of two main components: theoretical knowledge and practical application. In this context, the use of simulators is emphasized as playing a critical role, particularly during the initial stages of training. Simulator-supported applications serve an important function in developing the technical competencies of pilot candidates and enabling them to acquire fundamental flight operation skills within a risk-free and controlled environment.

Fig. 8. Changes in the proportions of human and technical failure in aviation accidents over time (1903–present) (Federal Aviation Administration, 2018)

In this context, numerous studies emphasize the need to update existing training programs and discuss various pedagogical approaches and alternative instructional strategies aimed at improving training curricula (Longridge et al., 2001; Vidakovic et al., 2021).

Aleksandrovich (2024) reiterates that the primary objective of pilot training is to ensure safe flight operations and argues that the process should progress through two dimensions: theoretical knowledge acquisition and practical application. In many studies, including that of Doolittle, the crash of Colgan Airlines Flight 3407 on February 12, 2009, is highlighted as a key event in justifying changes to flight training curricula. In this accident, the pilots responded incorrectly to an aerodynamic stall condition, causing the aircraft to lose control and resulting in a fatal accident that claimed the lives of 50 people. Following the accident, the flight-hour requirement for obtaining an Airline Transport Pilot (ATP) licence was significantly increased, with the aim of ensuring that pilot candidates undergo a more comprehensive and higher-quality training process (Doolittle, 2013).

After the Colgan Air 3407 accident, discussions regarding the quality of flight training intensified, and assessments suggesting that pilot training standards were inadequate prompted regulatory authorities to take action. In response to these developments, aviation authorities introduced comprehensive regulations aimed at more strictly standardizing pilot training processes. Within this framework, Part 141 – Pilot Schools, published under Title 14 of the Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) by the FAA, constitutes an important legal foundation, as it contains detailed provisions regarding the structure and content of pilot training as well as the responsibilities of training institutions (Arch, 2007; Graham, 2017).

While flight training was being restructured within this regulatory framework, various studies demonstrated that technological transformation also played a decisive role in shaping training standards. Arch (2020) argues that modern technologies such as glass cockpit systems, advanced simulation platforms, and synthetic vision systems have made fundamental changes in pilot training programs inevitable. To illustrate this transformation, the author notes that more than 60% of the training aircraft used by institutions affiliated with the University Aviation Association (UAA) fall within the Technically Advanced Aircraft (TAA) category. According to Arch, the integration of these technological innovations with flight simulation systems has the potential both to improve training efficiency and to significantly reduce training costs (Arch, 2007).

One of the most frequently emphasized approaches in the literature is Scenario-Based Training (SBT), which realistically models the operational challenges that pilots may encounter and focuses particularly on abnormal situations. Possebon et al. examined the integration of the SBT approach into initial flight training and argued that the traditional maneuver-based training philosophy has become insufficient to meet current needs in light of emerging technologies. Their study demonstrated that a scenario-based model, supported by advanced simulator technologies and structured around comprehensive flight missions, is more effective than a method based primarily on the repetition of specific maneuvers (Possebon et al., 2023). The same study presents a comparison between maneuver-based training and the SBT approach, which is shown in Table 4.

The practical learning structure provided by this method is regarded as an effective tool, particularly for developing critical competencies such as decision-making and situational awareness. The FAA has also incorporated this pedagogical approach and modern training technologies into the foundation of its FAA Industry Training Standards (FITS) program, aiming to systematically integrate scenario-based training into pilot training processes.

The effectiveness of the SBT approach, which forms the basis of this program, is supported by concrete findings reported in various studies. Research indicates that students participating in scenario-based training experience fewer interruptions during their training process. This improvement not only enhances operational efficiency but also results in approximately 9% savings in overall training costs.

These findings demonstrate that the SBT model contributes to pilot training not only from a pedagogical perspective but also from an economic standpoint (Robertson et al., 2005; Dornan et al., 2006).

Table 4.2. Comparison of Traditional Training and Scenario-Based Training (Possebon et al., 2023)

Criterion	Traditional Training (Maneuver-Based)	Scenario-Based Training (SBT)
Training Approach	Focused on individual maneuvers and procedures	Based on real mission scenarios
Task Completion Time	Long (on average approximately 17% longer)	Shorter and more efficient
Instructor Intervention Frequency	High	Significantly reduced
Unforeseen Error Rate	Low / Moderate	High
Knowledge and Skill Transfer	Low	High transfer from simulator to actual flight
Technology Used in Training	Low to medium-level simulators	FNPT II-class simulator
Instructor Control / Feedback	Limited control forms	Systematic through control documents

The systematic implementation of the SBT approach is reported to improve not only pilots' technical and operational skills but also cognitive competencies such as decision-making and situational awareness (Wiggins and Crognale, 2004). As reported by Pendleton, these benefits are also reflected in training duration and overall costs. According to the study, a training process that traditionally requires an average of 134 hours can be reduced to approximately 89 hours through the use of the SAFER (Situational Awareness For Enhanced Resilience) model, resulting in savings of approximately USD 6,000 (Gleb et al., 2014).

In this context, studies examining the strengths and limitations of simulator technology demonstrate that modern simulators enable pilots to undergo repeated training without the need for actual flight operations. Research emphasizes that the safe and controllable training environment provided by simulators makes the

process of knowledge and skill renewal more cost-effective while significantly reducing the risks associated with flight operations.

These findings clearly demonstrate that flight simulators have become indispensable tools not only during the initial stages of pilot training but also throughout the continuous training processes required over the course of a pilot's professional career (Balcerzak and Kostur, 2018).

4.3. The Role of Simulators in Pilots' Career Development

A substantial proportion of studies addressing pilot career development indicate that simulator-supported training plays a critical role throughout pilots' career progression, beginning from their entry into the profession. These publications examine in detail the process of preparation for the aviation industry, the acquisition of operational competencies, and continuous professional development.

The career theme is generally discussed not only in terms of professional advancement but also in conjunction with cost and training dimensions, emphasizing that these three elements are closely interconnected and cannot be considered independently. The literature frequently highlights the global pilot shortage and argues that factors such as lengthy training programs, high costs, and limited training capacity increasingly complicate efforts to address this shortage (Herchko, 2012; Amornpipat, 2023; Fanjoy, 2002; Al-Romaihi, 2006).

In this context, the literature emphasizes that integrating simulator-based training with traditional flight training through various implementation models provides substantial time and cost advantages in both initial and recurrent training processes.

The reviewed studies demonstrate that pilot training is not limited to the acquisition of technical skills but also encompasses the development of cognitive and behavioral competencies such as crew coordination, decision-making, and situational awareness. This comprehensive structure requires pilots not only to develop technical knowledge and flight skills but also to collaborate effectively and harmoniously with other personnel involved in flight operations. In addition, pilots must acquire cognitive and behavioral competencies such as crisis management, decision-making, and situational awareness in order to respond appropriately to abnormal situations and maintain flight safety.

In response to these requirements, simulator-based approaches designed to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of training processes have gained increasing importance. One of the most prominent models in the literature, the FAA Industry Training Standards (FITS) program, positions simulator use not merely as a supplementary tool but as a central component of the training process.

The reviewed studies indicate that models such as FITS significantly enhance both the technical competencies and cognitive performance of pilot candidates and pilots undergoing recurrent training. Furthermore, these training approaches have been shown to provide considerable time and cost savings for both institutions and individuals by substantially reducing the total duration required for flight training (Callender et al., 2009).

One of the most important contributions of simulator-based programs is their ability to enable pilots to rapidly develop higher-order competencies such as decision-making, problem-solving, and situational awareness through scenarios that closely replicate real flight environments. Numerous studies in the literature have demonstrated that pilot candidates participating in such programs exhibit higher performance levels and greater readiness for flight duties compared with those trained through traditional methods (Balcerzak and Kostur, 2018; Beckman et al., 2008; Blackmon and Polson, 2002; Callender et al., 2009; Dekker, 2011; Dornan et al., 2006; Michael et al., 2022; Nowakowski and Makarewicz, 2018; Oolbekkink, 2006; Possebon et al., 2023; Taylor et al., 2005; Thomas, 2016; Vidakovic et al., 2021).

The rapid advancement of simulation technologies further demonstrates that these benefits are not limited to the initial stages of training. Today, flight simulators are used as primary training tools throughout various phases of pilot education. In some cases, they significantly reduce the need for actual flight training, while in programs such as type-rating training, they can even facilitate the completion of the entire training process within a simulator environment (Balcerzak and Kostur, 2018; Kozuba and Bondaruk, 2014). This clearly demonstrates

that simulator-based training has become a critical tool throughout all stages of a pilot's career from pedagogical, financial, and operational perspectives.

Flight simulators not only contribute to the development of pilots' technical competencies but also directly influence their career development processes. The literature indicates that simulator-based training enhances skills that are critical for professional competence, including decision-making, problem-solving, and situational awareness (Kozuba and Bondaruk, 2014). Moreover, the widespread use of simulators in various training stages, such as instrument flight training, commercial pilot licence training, and type-rating programs, enables training processes to be completed more rapidly and allows pilots to begin their professional careers at an earlier stage (Nowakowski and Makarewicz, 2018; Balcerzak and Kostur, 2018). In addition, scenario-based and simulator-supported training models are reported to improve the effectiveness of pilot training and contribute to alleviating the pilot shortage currently faced by the aviation industry (Graham, 2017; Arch, 2007). From this perspective, simulators are regarded as important tools not only during initial training but also for the development, maintenance, and assessment of professional competencies throughout pilots' careers.

These developments have also shaped the perspectives of regulatory authorities regarding simulator use and played a decisive role in the restructuring of aviation training systems. Indeed, the study by Nowakowski and Makarewicz (2018) clearly demonstrates the extent to which simulator integration is possible within EASA's Part-FCL (Flight Crew Licensing) regulations. The study indicates that approximately 70% of Instrument Rating (IR) training may be completed in simulators, with the potential to reduce training costs by nearly half.

A similar degree of flexibility exists for Airline Transport Pilot Licence (ATPL) programs. For example, approximately 40 hours of the 150 flight hours required for ATPL training—equivalent to around 26%—may be completed using Full Flight Simulators (FFS) or Flight and Navigation Procedures Trainers (FNPT II). Furthermore, according to Part-FCL regulations, up to 100 of the 1,500 flight hours required for ATPL certification may be completed using FNPT II or Flight Training Device (FTD) Level 2–3 simulators, while up to 200 hours may be credited when Full Flight Simulators are utilized (EASA, 2020).

These regulations clearly demonstrate that simulator-based training occupies a central position in a pilot's career not only because of its pedagogical effectiveness but also because it has become a legally recognized and standards-compliant component of aviation training.

5. Conclusion

This systematic literature review examined the effects of flight simulators on pilot training, cost structures, and career development within a multidimensional framework. The findings indicate that training occupies a dominant position in the literature, while the themes of cost and career are generally addressed in direct relation to training. The results reveal that, despite modern technological advancements, accidents caused by human error continue to occur at a significant rate, highlighting the need for continuous improvements in pilot training programs. This finding clearly demonstrates why simulators have become critical tools in aviation training, as they enable the reinforcement of technical and cognitive skills through risk-free scenarios.

Although the advantages of simulators have been extensively discussed in the literature, it is frequently emphasized that this technology alone is insufficient and that meaningful learning outcomes can only be achieved when simulator-based training is integrated with a strong theoretical foundation. Some studies identify limitations related to motion systems, visual quality, and physical feedback as disadvantages, arguing that simulators cannot fully replicate real-time flight responses. Nevertheless, their ability to provide a safe environment for practicing complex and hazardous maneuvers has made simulators indispensable components of modern aviation training.

From a cost perspective, the high initial investment required for simulator acquisition emerges as one of the primary factors limiting both institutional capacity and accessibility to pilot training. However, the higher costs associated with actual flight operations, together with aircraft maintenance and operational expenses, make simulators financially advantageous for institutions in the long term. Despite these benefits, high acquisition costs and limited infrastructure continue to contribute to the global pilot shortage. This situation has encouraged national and international aviation authorities to develop more efficient, shorter, and technology-based training

models. In this regard, pedagogical approaches such as Scenario-Based Training (SBT) and Competency-Based Training and Assessment (CBTA) have gained increasing prominence.

When all findings are considered collectively, flight simulators demonstrate strong potential to improve the quality of pilot training, reduce operational risks, optimize training duration, and support the development of professional competencies. Nevertheless, the review also indicates that studies addressing the disadvantages of simulator use remain relatively limited. Issues such as simulator sickness, differences between simulator and real-flight responses, and motivational challenges require further investigation. In addition, the high cost of simulators continues to represent a significant barrier for both institutions and students. Therefore, future research should address not only technical and pedagogical dimensions but also accessibility, cost-reduction strategies, and inter-institutional collaboration.

In conclusion, simulator-based training plays a central role in pilot development processes. However, realizing its full potential requires more comprehensive research, stronger institutional cooperation, and broader financial support mechanisms. Standards jointly developed by educational institutions and aviation authorities will contribute to making simulator technology more effective and accessible, while also representing an important step toward alleviating the global pilot shortage.

In this context, the present study aims to provide a systematic synthesis of findings related to simulator use that have previously been addressed in a fragmented manner within the literature, thereby offering a valuable resource for both academic and practical purposes. In particular, the holistic analysis conducted across the dimensions of training, cost, and career development provides concrete evidence to support the more efficient and sustainable restructuring of aviation education policies. Accordingly, the study not only fills an important gap in the literature but also offers recommendations that may contribute to decision-making processes within aviation training institutions and regulatory authorities.

Author Statement

Hursit Deniz Özerdoğan: Conceptualization, methodology, literature review, data collection, formal analysis, writing – original draft preparation.

Tamer Savaş: Supervision, validation, review and editing, final approval of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

(10p Aptos Narrow) The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Ethical approval

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